

IMPROVING READING COMPREHENSION, VOCABULARY AND FLUENCY THROUGH THE USE OF BOTTOM-UP MODEL: AN EXPERIMENT

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 22

Issue 8

Pages: 983-991

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2115

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13126616

Manuscript Accepted: 07-21-2024

Improving Reading Comprehension, Vocabulary and Fluency through the Use of Bottom-Up Model: An Experiment

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Abstract

This study aimed to investigate the effects of the bottom-up model on students' reading comprehension, vocabulary, and fluency. A quasi-experimental pretest-posttest group design was utilized, comparing the experimental group, which received the bottom-up model method on improving reading comprehension, vocabulary, and fluency, with the control group, which received traditional or lecture strategy. Class proficiency and t-tests were employed as statistical approaches to assess the significance of the experimental and control groups. Both groups underwent pre-tests and post-tests, with the experimental group receiving the intervention. The results indicated that there was significant difference in comprehension, vocabulary and fluency between the pretest and posttest for the control group. However, there was a significant difference in the comprehension, vocabulary and fluency between the pretest and posttest for the experimental group higher than the result of the posttest in control group. This indicates that the treatment is way more effective than the traditional method of control group. Additionally, there was a significant difference in comprehension between the post-tests of the experimental and control groups. These findings suggest that the bottom-up model effectively enhanced students' reading comprehension, vocabulary and fluency. Therefore, the study concluded that the use of the bottom-up model was recommended as an intervention for improving reading comprehension skills, vocabulary and fluency.

Keywords: *reading strategy, reading comprehension, vocabulary, fluency, bottom-up model*

Introduction

Learning to read is one of the most fundamental skills or abilities that every student must obtain. Students need to learn to read so they can learn about many things from their environment and it facilitates them how to function in the community where they are in. The ability to read well is crucial for students to succeed in the classroom because it gives them the opportunity to improve their communication and linguistic abilities. As explained by Noor (2011) that reading is the most fundamental academic skill. It is a common knowledge that students who could not read will experience difficulty in answering the test during examination period. They will be in trouble in comprehending lectures or even reading information in the textbook or modules.

Further, a study was conducted which aimed to evaluate the effectiveness of intensive reading intervention based on the standardized test scores that was implemented in a rural community in Northern California, USA. The study addressed the challenge of meeting the objective of increasing student performance in reading that was reflected on the standardized test. It investigated whether or not there was a significant relationship between students receiving the intensive reading intervention and positive academic growth as it is measured on the standardized test. This study did not find significance between the intensive reading intervention and an increase in the standardized test that was given to the subjects of the study who were enrolled in the intervention (Erickson, 2013).

A study by Pocaan et al. (2022) titled "Strategic Reading Intervention for Left-Behind Learners in the Philippines" found that struggling readers initially had a frustration-level reading ability. The remedial program, using strategic intervention materials with four parts—learning content, learning task guide, assessment guide, and enhancement guide—improved the participants' reading ability to instructional and independent levels. It recommended that school leaders and program specialists develop support programs to enhance student literacy.

The researcher who worked as a teacher at Depot Elementary School observed that her Grade 6 students have low level of reading comprehension. Because of this teachers have to devise the best techniques to increase their reading comprehension. This problem is not only faced by small group of teachers but this is also experienced and felt by the greater majority of the teachers both in public and private school teachers. Parents of these students are also concerned about how to assist their children to read and to comprehend what they have read. This is the reason that the researcher is convinced to use the bottom up model to improve reading performance which includes comprehension, fluency, and vocabulary.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the effectiveness of the bottom-up model on the reading comprehension, vocabulary, and fluency of elementary pupils of Depot Elementary School in Monkayo, Davao De Oro. Specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the performance of Grade 6 students in reading comprehension, vocabulary, and fluency during the pretest of:
 - 1.1. control and
 - 1.2. experimental groups
2. What is the performance of Grade 6 students in reading comprehension, vocabulary, and fluency during the posttest of:

- 2.1. control group
- 2.2. experimental group
3. Is there a significant difference between the pretest and posttest of the control group in reading comprehension, vocabulary, and fluency?
4. Is there a significant difference between the pretest and posttest of the experimental group in reading comprehension, vocabulary, and fluency?
5. Is there a significant difference between the posttest of the control group and experimental in reading comprehension, vocabulary, and fluency?

Methodology

Research Design

The study employed a quantitative quasi-experimental two-group pretest-posttest research design. This design was chosen because it allows for manipulation of the independent variable before measuring the dependent variable, thereby addressing the directionality issue typical in observational studies (Cook & Campbell, 1979). Although participants were not randomized to conditions, which could introduce confounding variables, this design was deemed suitable for this study's objectives (Maciejewski, 2018).

Respondents for this study were selected based on specific criteria to ensure relevance to the research objectives. The appropriateness of this sample was considered in relation to the study's design and goals, aiming to minimize biases and ensure meaningful results. The selection criteria were designed to reflect the target population's characteristics relevant to the variables under investigation, aligning with the principles of quantitative quasi-experimental research.

Respondents

The subjects of this study were the 46 Grade 6 students of Depot Elementary School who are enrolled for the school year 2023-2024. The section will be subjected to this quantitative quasi-experimental research with 31 males and 15 females. These students were divided in two groups. The first group was the control group with 23 students and the experimental group with 23 students. The distribution of the students per group was done through simple sampling technique. The researcher was very careful in doing the selection process since it was very important to distribute those students who were fast learners. The students were distributed based on the process adopted by the researcher.

Instruments

The pretest and posttest utilized in this study consisted of researcher-developed assessments designed to evaluate reading comprehension, vocabulary, and fluency among the study subjects. The research questions were categorized into three sections: Test I assessed reading comprehension with 15 items, Test II evaluated vocabulary with 15 items, and Test III measured fluency with another 15 items. A Table of Specifications (TOS) was created to outline how the questions were distributed based on their level of difficulty. The questionnaire used a multiple-choice format with four options per item, totaling 45 items. This instrument served both as the pretest and posttest for the study.

Validation of Instrument

The validation process involved presenting the test questionnaire to validators identified by the Dean of the Graduate School, who provided feedback and suggestions for improvement. The revised instrument was then administered to the predetermined study group according to scheduled sessions. This iterative process ensured that the questionnaire accurately measured the intended variables. Issues identified during validation were thoroughly investigated, and necessary adjustments to the items were made based on validator feedback.

The pretest and posttest instruments, along with their Table of Specifications, underwent rigorous validation processes that included item analysis, reliability testing, and validity testing using appropriate statistical methods. A pilot test involving 20 students divided into upper and lower score groups provided data for assessing item difficulty, discrimination, and effectiveness of response options. Results from these analyses were reviewed and refined through feedback from peers, advisors, and other relevant authorities to finalize the instruments for use in the study.

Procedure

The researcher commenced their study by securing necessary approvals from the office of the division superintendent of Davao de Oro and subsequently obtaining permission from the school principal to conduct their research. The experimentation phase commenced with subjects divided into control and experimental groups, each undergoing pretests before implementing the respective teaching methods. Following the study, posttests were administered to both groups to assess the effectiveness of the intervention. Throughout the process, the researcher adhered to ethical standards, ensuring participant confidentiality, data security, and rigorous statistical analysis overseen by a professional statistician.

Moreover, the study strictly adhered to Republic Act No. 10173, safeguarding participant privacy and ensuring informed consent procedures were followed meticulously. Measures were implemented to mitigate risks to participants' well-being, and guidelines against plagiarism and data fabrication were strictly enforced to uphold academic integrity. Conflict of interest was actively managed to maintain research impartiality, and authorship rights were respected in accordance with Republic Act No. 8293, acknowledging contributions from advisors and collaborators in the research process. These ethical considerations ensured the study was conducted with transparency, reliability, and respect for all stakeholders involved.

Data Analysis

Statistical treatment of data is essential in experimental research. This helps in the analysis of data and to arrive at the appropriate conclusions.

Mean. Mean was used to measure the central tendency between the pretest and posttest mean scores in the control group and experimental group.

Paired t-test. The formula for a paired t-test, also known as a dependent t-test, compares the means of two related groups to determine if there is a statistically significant difference between their means.

Independent t-test. The independent t-test (also known as the two-sample t-test) compares the means of two independent groups to determine if there is a statistically significant difference between their means.

Another statistical tool used was the Kuder-Richardson Formula 20. This was used to test the reliability of the research instruments.

Results and Discussion

The Pretest Scores of the Group

Table 1 shows the Mean Comparison of Pretest Scores of Control and Experimental Groups.

Table 1. Mean Competency of Pre-test Scores of Control and Experimental Group

<i>Pre-test</i>	<i>No. of Students</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>Class Proficiency</i>	<i>Competency level</i>
Control group	23	1.087	2.021	7.8%	No mastery of skills
Experimental group	23	1.739	2.115	12.4%	No mastery of skills

Table 1 shows that the mean pretest score in control group is 1.087 with 2.021 standard deviation and the experimental group has mean pretest score of 1.739 with standard deviation of 2.115. The mean difference is only 0.652. The class proficiency of the control group is 7.8% with a competency level of no mastery. The class proficiency of experimental group is 12.4% with a class proficiency of no mastery of skills. Both groups have similar levels of proficiency in the pretest. The data presented shows that the mean scores for both groups in the pretest are relatively similar, with the Experimental Group having a slightly higher mean score. However, both groups showed no mastery of skills level in reading comprehension.

The Posttest Scores of the Groups

Table 2 shows the Mean Comparison of Posttest Scores of Control and Experimental Group.

Table 2. Mean Competency of Posttest Scores of Control and Experimental Group

<i>Posttest</i>	<i>No. of Students</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>Class Proficiency</i>	<i>Competency level</i>
Control group	23	5.435	3.824	39.5%	No mastery of skills
Experimental group	23	10.609	4.325	76%	Mastery of skills

Table 2 shows the posttest scores in the control and experimental group. It was revealed that the mean posttest score of the control group is 5.435 and a standard deviation of 3.824 and the experimental group has a mean posttest score of 10.609 with standard deviation of 4.325. This further indicates that the class proficiency of the posttest score of the control and experimental groups are 39.5% and 76%. This implies that both groups improved their skills in reading comprehension, vocabulary and fluency after the intervention. The class proficiency indicates that the experimental group has a higher competency level than control group.

Significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores of the control group

Table 3 presents the significant difference between pretest and posttest scores of the control group.

Table 3. Pretest and Posttest of the Control Group

<i>Control group</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>t-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
Pretest	1.087	4.646	<.001	Significant
Posttest	5.435			

Paired t-test was used to test if there is a significant difference in the pretest and posttest of control. For the control group, the mean of the pretest is 1.087 and the mean of the posttest is 5.435, p-value is 0.001 which is lower than the 0.05 level of significance therefore

there is significant difference between the pretest and posttest mean score of the control group.

The data clearly indicates that there is improvement between the performance of the students during the pretest against their performance during the posttest of the control group in traditional strategy.

Significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores of the experimental group

Table 4 shows the results of paired t-test of the students' pretest and posttest in the experimental group.

Table 4. *Pretest and Posttest of Experimental Group*

<i>Experimental group</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>t-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
Pretest	1.739	12.128	<.001	Significant
Posttest	10.6			

Paired t-test was used to test if there is a significant difference in the pretest and posttest of the experimental group mean. The result is clearly stated in the table that pretest mean is 1.739 and posttest mean is 10.6 with a t-value of 12.128 which higher with a p-value of 0.001 which is less than the level of significance at 0.05. This result suggests that there is a significant difference between the performance of the students in the experimental group during the pretest and posttest. Thus, the experimental group showed a significant improvement in their scores during the posttest. The data suggests that the intervention or treatment administered which is the bottom-up model had a positive effect on their performance.

Significant difference between posttest scores of students in control and experimental group. Table 5 shows the results of independent t-test of the posttest of control group and experimental group

Table 5. *Posttest of Control and Experimental Group*

<i>Post-test</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>t-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
Control	5.435	4.298	0.001	Significant
Experimental	10.6			

An independent t-test was used to test if there is significant difference in the posttest of the control and experimental group, mean posttest of control is 5.435 and the mean posttest of experimental group is 10.6 p-value is 0.001 which is less than 0.05, significant which means that the null hypothesis is rejected since there is a significant difference between the posttest of the control and experimental groups.

Mean Competency of Pre-test Scores of Control and Experimental Group. Based on the result of the pretest score in reading comprehension, vocabulary and fluency both groups are not performing well, and they show no mastery of skills. Before the intervention, the students in the control and experimental groups were not good in reading comprehension, vocabulary and fluency.

This is in parallel to the result of the study of Gilakjani & Sabouri (2016), readers must identify the elements that will influence their interpretation of the material they are reading. Furthermore, readers should apply a variety of reading strategies while reading the text. All these characteristics and tactics should be developed to make the reading process simple and effective.

Mean Competency of Posttest Scores of Control and Experimental Group. Both the control and experimental groups increased their performance in reading comprehension, vocabulary and fluency. However, the experimental group shows improvement in their performance as compared with the performance of the control group. Furthermore, the data suggests that the bottom-up model as an intervention had a positive effect of the students' competency level when compared to the control group.

This is parallel to the study of Haniff & Heriyawati (2024), indicated that most of the students gave positive response toward the use of Bottom-Up approach in teaching reading. It emphasized that the approach could improve students' ability in reading, effective, interesting, and grab the students' enthusiasm in reading activity

Significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores of the control group. When the control group was post tested it was found out that the result increased which means that the performance of the students improved even if they are not exposed the bottom-up model. Though they were taught using the traditional way of teaching still the students' performance have increase. It shows that the students are already used to the traditional way of teaching developing comprehension, vocabulary and fluency.

According to Wang (2022). The quick progression of the times has also brought more advanced Educational approaches and concepts. Many experts advocate for the replacement of traditional educational techniques with more modern ones. The study suggests that current educational methods offer more benefits, but teachers must choose the best method for their students based on their condition, goals, and probable hurdles.

Additionally, Traditional methods, often known as conventional education, are frequently employed in schools. Perse (2017) describes the traditional method of teaching in which the instructor is the source of ideas and information, and the student receives and interacts with them as a knowledge recipient.

Nevertheless, both conventional and modern teaching approaches are successful and valuable in today's school. It all comes down to

balance, as it does in most situations. Teachers must recognize when traditional methods are most effective and when it is appropriate to explore new and innovative ones. (Mehta

2019).

Significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores of the experimental group. There was an increase of the posttest result of the experimental group. They were exposed to bottom-up model although the control group had improved their performance using the traditional way but the increase of the performance of the experimental group is far better than the control group. This means that using the bottom-up model is better than the traditional way.

This is parallel to Pourhosein et al. (2016) that readers construct a meaningful representation of a text using effective reading strategies. Finding the most appropriate reading strategies is a significant skill to the students' reading comprehension.

Moreover, Richards-Tutor et al. (2016) stated that interventions had generally positive effects on reading outcomes such as comprehension (reading cloze, reading passages, listening comprehension), phonological awareness (PA), phonics/word reading, and fluency.

Significant difference between posttest scores of students in control and experimental group. The data revealed that the control group posttest result is inferior as compared with the experimental group.

Therefore, based on the results, it can be concluded that the intervention applied to the experimental group had a significant effect on the posttest scores compared to control group which is using the traditional way of teaching comprehension skill, vocabulary, and fluency. The experimental group performed significantly better than the control group in the posttest. This proves that there was a significant difference between the reading comprehension, vocabulary, and fluency of the students when using the bottom-up model in improving students' comprehension, vocabulary, and fluency.

This is in connection with the findings Perez, et al., (2016), Implementation of Bottom-up strategy as classroom project to develop and promote learners' reading comprehension skills in a fourth grade in a public school in Cartago. Comprehension plays an important role in the language learning process considering that reading is one of four language skills. Thus, this project could be used as a model for future lessons in which teachers want to improve students' reading comprehension skills in the English language.

Furthermore, Moskovsky, (2014) conducted a research quasi-experimental design to assess the relative effectiveness of two modes of academic English vocabulary instruction, bottom-up and top-down. Analyses of the test scores reveal that at the bottom-up group slightly outperformed the top-down one on both vocabulary size and controlled productive knowledge. The group used the bottom-up showed superiority and was found to be statically significant.

Conclusions

It can be concluded that the bottom-up model is a good intervention strategy in teaching the students who are not good in reading comprehension, vocabulary, and fluency. However, the traditional way of teaching also showed significant improvements on the performance of the students but students who are exposed to this strategy are quite inferior as compared to those who were exposed to bottom-up model. Hence, bottom-up model is an effective instructional strategy that can enhance the ability of the pupils in dealing with reading comprehension, vocabulary, and fluency the faster and easier way.

The following recommendations are hereby presented:

Bottom-up model based on the result is an effective instructional strategy, particularly on the reading comprehension, vocabulary and fluency skills of the pupils. It is recommended to adopt the strategy to classroom instructions as an alternate method.

Further study, such as qualitative research, is recommended to further check the effectiveness of bottom-up model in developing the comprehension, vocabulary, and fluency of the students.

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